

THE ROLE OF ART THERAPY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AESTHETIC COMPETENCE OF FUTURE VISUAL ARTS TEACHERS

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Abstract: Creativity itself makes human life interesting and rich. By expressing oneself, a person can look at himself from the outside, look at the problem situation from a different angle. When drawing, a person transfers his inner world to the drawing.

Keywords: creativity, Art therapy, visual circle, aesthetic competence.

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All our unspoken thoughts are blocked in the body, and this leads to physical and neurotic disorders. Cutting out emotions and sensations on canvas, on paper, in dance, a person helps himself, his body to get rid of unnecessary “blocks” and stay alive. Its creative manifestation is a path to oneself, an opportunity to successfully build one's own life. When undergoing Art therapy, a person repeats himself unconscious visual expression. Each person feels the need to express himself, and when creating something, he feels satisfaction, as if he finds harmony in himself.

Art therapy is one of the modern directions of psychotherapy, which, when translated into Russian, means “art-treatment”. The term was first used by Adrian Hill in 1938 and soon became widespread. Often, art therapy is understood as the visual framework of art, that is, what is seen by the eye. The effectiveness of this technique is that it allows you to experiment with emotions, study and express them on a symbolic level. Art therapy is a journey into your subconscious. Like dreams, he reveals to a person what is hidden in the hidden corners of his soul.

In Art therapy, works are not evaluated and compared. This is an important point. It is difficult for an adult to decide on self-expression, and he needs to be supported when he takes the first step and decides on therapy. The task of the therapist is to create a situation in which a person himself can understand the meaning of his problems and find a way out of them, look at the problem in a new way.

Art therapy is considered one of the safest and safest DDI methods... It uses auditory, visual and tactile analyzers and this, in turn, helps to improve both the

physical and the emotional state of the person. This treatment scheme is suitable for both children and adult patients. The types of Art therapy are diverse, and can be replaced often in the process of treatment, a person is engaged in painting, photography and music. So you can forget about boring activities, because art therapy is a guarantee of a pleasant rest. The technique allows you to use completely different (often not very expensive) materials, conduct Sessions not only in the doctor's office, but also in other places and, if desired, even outdoors. It is these factors that make art therapy very popular. In the United States and some European countries, such correction methods are used everywhere. With the help of art, people successfully cope with post-traumatic stress disorder, aggression, withdrawal, stiffness, depression, hyperactivity and many other problems. Most often, a person has difficulty verbally expressing his thoughts and feelings. The necessary words do not come to my mind or a continuous line runs in my head at the speed of light, and it seems that my brain is bursting. A person is not able to form his own feelings, cannot find a positive path for his feelings, something worries him, worries him. And here comes to the rescue art therapy. A person may not even know the name of the action in which the unconscious steps; he takes a brush, oil, canvas, and after a few hours he feels a slight pain behind his back, and order comes to his head - thoughts that excite the brain fade into the background and spread throughout his body. Each cell, a wonderful harmony. What is it? This can be called creativity therapy or art therapy. The term "art therapy" (Art therapy) was coined by artist Adrian Hill in 1938, when working with patients, he noticed that creative activity distracts patients from their experiences and helps them cope with the disease. Word combination "art therapy" (art (English) - art, therapeia (yun.)- care, treatment) is understood as care. Emotional well-being of a person through psychological health and creativity.

Everyone has the ability to express themselves creatively, but growing up, a person often loses this ability, forbids himself to dance, paint, rub his hands with clay, closes his creative potential and limits his life, hinders. Emotional manifestations... We all ask ourselves one day - "Who Am I? What am I?", but creative self-expression is able to evoke the strongest constructive feelings in a person, which leads to the release of emotional impulses.

Expressing yourself through art is a painless way to express emotions. Art therapy has no restrictions or contraindications, being a safe way to relieve stress. This natural way is healing, negative emotions become positive. Art therapy sessions give strength, confidence and help you find a way out of a dead end. The use of artistic creation helps to increase self-esteem and a worthy acceptance of oneself in society. In the process of creativity, many problems arise that are deeply hidden, and they are solved painlessly. Thus, drawing helps a person to abstract from their problems and feelings and look at them from the outside.

Art therapy. This is to buy more harmony, personal development than cure. Just as there are many directions in art, the same number of directions can be distinguished in art therapy. Writing fairy tales, drawing, dancing, singing, working with ceramics, game Therapy, Mask therapy, sand therapy, color therapy, doll making, phototherapy, music therapy, etc.

Therapy is another popular technique, since color shades are of great importance for people. For example, in ancient times, Warriors applied a combat dye to the body, which should evoke horror on the enemy. Color and feeling are intertwined. In addition, certain tones directly affect the work of the body. At the time of scientific research scientists were able to prove that, for example, dark blue helps to calm down, and red and orange, on the contrary, contribute to excitement. High blood pressure, increased heart rate, deep breathing, etc. A combination of different shades, contrasting colors will help create a certain mood, express their thoughts and use visual analyzers.

In recent years, art therapy has become an excellent way to solve various psychological problems. "Art healing" is effective and useful, therefore it is widely used in working with patients, regardless of age. Of course, any information is interesting to many. For example, what such correction methods look like, What are its types. Art therapy has practically no restrictions and contraindications, but it allows you to achieve really good results.

There are no restrictions on the use of Art therapy. Art therapy can use any psychological theories and models. Only the language of communication is not only words, but also artistic images, body movements, musical sounds. Therapy can be applied to work with any problem, it can be done with interethnic conflicts, with interethnic conflicts, examples can be given for a very long time. Art therapy is working with children who are unable to reflect their feelings and feelings with the elderly, improving their quality of life, with victims who are in a state of shock. In any case, it will concern the improvement of the state, the expansion of opportunities, the development of self-government, etc.

Types of Art therapy.

This method is of increased interest, which leads to the fact that its boundaries expand and all new "tools" of therapeutic art appear. The methods of art therapy are as follows:

- Isotherapy-painting and drawing;
- Color therapy - each person is exposed to the light of different colors from each other;
- Music therapy living in listening to various compositions;
- Sandy therapy-drawing with sand;
- Video therapy - Hero means watching a video that has the same problem in the form of;

- Games - in the game process, the necessary mental functions are formed;
- Bliturpia-this method uses literature to treat the word;
- Fairy tale therapy-the composition of the fairy tale, analysis of existing works;
- Mascotherapy-a picture around the patient's face, which allows you to direct the patient's face in the right channel, emotions and experience;
- Dramaherapy, that is, dramatization, playing on any plot;
- Phototherapy-photos, collages;
- Dance therapy-dance;
- Art-stalpesheapia - this is a picture, which combines sewing, cartoon, color, mask, phototherapy, etc.

Art therapy affects the psyche gently, carelessly, since the healing process is similar to a hobby. Often the patient is in a tubidic state, it is difficult to establish contact, and the possibilities of art therapy allow you to demonstrate "I" through your visual art. Such a method of treatment is reflected due to the fact that the content of the patient in the patient is reflected in him when drawing, dancing or singing, as a result of which the state of the psyche is harmonized. Such treatment does not lead to rejection or rejection client, which is very important for people in a state of stress. It is always optional and safe. In the process of designing internal experiences in its creation, the subconscious does not know that they come out unconsciously. If we consider the process from the point of view of psychoanalysis, then its main mechanism is sublimation. Through artistic pictures and objects, the interaction of the subconscious mind occurs, and the therapist helps the patient to understand the "fainting" for him.

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